

EFFECT OF AGEING ON THE CONDUCTIVITY OF SOLS

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In this paper the changes in electrical conductivity of the sols of stannic hydroxide, ferric phosphate and vanadium pentoxide on ageing have been investigated. The nature of the changes taking place in this property, depends upon the behaviour of colloidal particles and concentration of the sol. The changes have been more prominent in the case of most dilute sols. In general the adsorption capacity of the particles decreases on ageing, resulting in an increase in electrical conductivity except in some cases where some of the substances present in solution, polymerises to give some complex aggregates, causing a decrease in conductivity.

It is well known that the physical properties of colloids considerably change on ageing. Gessner (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1924, 19, 213,) studied the properties of vanadium pentoxide sol in detail and noted a decrease in conductivity with time. Rocasolano ("Colloid Chemistry" by J. Alexander, Vol. II, p. 99) found that the electrical conductivity of colloids vary within wide limits; an increase in the case of silver sol and a decrease in the case of calf-serum was noted by him. Dhar and Chakarvarti (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 120; *Z. anorg. Chem.* 1927, 168, 209) have reported the effect of ageing on the electrical conductivity of sols and concluded that in general lyophobic sols show an increase while lyophilic ones show a decrease in electrical conductivity. Lottermoser and Lesche (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1931, 32, 157) have observed that the electrical conductivity of ferric hydroxide sol, which is usually regarded as lyophobic sol, increases on ageing. Similarly Desai and co-workers (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1939, 2, ii, 39) report that in general the sols of arsenious sulphides, gold and vanadium pentoxide decrease in their electric charges on ageing as obtained from cataphoretic speed measurements. These sols also become unstable to some of the coagulating electrolytes and the specific conductivity generally decreases on ageing of the sols. In this paper we have studied the effect of ageing on the conductivity of some sols of different purities and concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

For conductivity measurements Rowland's bridge was used. In place of the induction coil, an electrically operated tuning fork of low frequency was used. The conductivity cell was well-platinised so as to give sharp minimum points. The conductivity was found at 30° by placing the cell in a thermostat in which the temperature could be easily adjusted to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The bridge was calibrated for the cell constant using the modified method of Wark (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 885). Graph for the cell constant and different readings of the bridge was plotted and the value of cell constant corresponding to any bridge reading was obtained from the graph. A higher order of accuracy may be obtained by employing this method as illustrated below. Results obtained by taking the mean cell constant are also given for comparison.

TABLE I
N/10-KCl solution. Temp. -30° .

Resistance in ohms.	Bridge reading.	Cell constant.	Sp. condy. with mean cell const.	Sp. condy. from graph.
2	86.5	0.1871	0.01520	0.01481
3	81.3	0.1914	0.01483	0.01466
4	76.85	0.1936	0.01468	0.01459
5	72.5	0.1924	0.01478	0.01459
10	57.35	0.1966	0.01446	0.01459
15	47.55	0.1985	0.01433	0.01469
17	44.3	0.1972	0.01443	0.01480
20	40.3	0.1971	0.01448	0.01480
25	35.1	0.1973	0.01441	0.01469
27	33.45	0.1981	0.01436	0.01480
30	31	0.2032	0.01400	0.01469
35	27.95	0.1985	0.01505	0.01459
40	25.35	0.1992	0.01485	0.01469

It is evident from the above, that the error is very much reduced by using this method, and the results are practically constant.

Stannic Hydroxide Sol

The sol was prepared as mentioned in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 23). The various samples of sol at different stages of purity (A, A', A'', A''') were taken out and diluted to their one-third and one-ninth concentration and stocked in the same way. The results of specific conductivity as measured at 30° are given below.

TABLE II

Conc. of sol A = 45.16 g/l.
Conc. of $(\text{NH}_4)^+$ = 1.36 g/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy $\times 10^3$ mho		
	Sol A.	Sol A'/3.	Sol A'/9.
0	2.350	0.819	0.306
7	2.289	0.903	0.370
20	2.220	0.910	0.489
45	2.189	0.9202	0.480
61	2.211	0.8686	0.5496
102	2.255	0.9913	0.6101

TABLE III

Conc. of sol A = 42.40 g/l.
Conc. of $(\text{NH}_4)^+$ = 0.823 g/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^3$ mho		
	Sol A'.	Sol A'/3.	Sol A'/9.
0	1.340	0.431	0.1821
6	1.300	0.559	0.2130
19	1.257	0.5760	0.2350
44	1.140	0.5459	0.2299
59	1.187	0.5730	0.2441
102	1.290	0.6235	0.2845

TABLE IV

Conc. of sol A' = 36.58 g/l.
Conc. of (NH₄)⁺ = 0.501 g/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^{-3}$ mho		
	Sol A'.	Sol A''/g.	Sol A'''/g.
0	0.887	0.2996	0.113
14	0.789	0.3860	0.1581
21	0.789	0.4550	0.1780
43	0.7541	0.3542	0.1847
57	0.7877	0.3661	0.1904
99	0.8184	0.3990	0.2036

TABLE V

Conc. of the Sol A''' = 33.92 g/l.
Conc. of (NH₄)⁺ = 0.295 g/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^{-3}$ mho		
	Sol A'''.	Sol A''''/g.	Sol. A''''/g.
0	0.5740	0.224	0.0978
10	0.5725	0.255	0.1140
21	0.5300	0.256	0.1180
43	0.5146	0.262	0.1239
52	0.5337	0.2679	0.1263
90	0.5400	0.2720	0.1304

TABLE VI

Conc. of sol B = 51.52 g/l.
Conc. of Cl ion = 0.236 g. ion/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^3$ mho		
	Sol B.	Sol B/g.	Sol B/g.
0	32.61	15.63	6.80
12	33.40	16.36	7.72
33	32.29	16.01	6.86
50	32.16	15.55	6.404
65	32.49	15.43	6.299

TABLE VII

Conc. of sol B' = 37.30 g/l.
Conc. of Cl ion = 0.096 g. ion/l.

No. of days.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^3$ mho		
	Sol B'.	Sol B'/g.	Sol B'/g.
0	12.55	5.95	2.72
10	13.12	6.372	2.89
21	13.02	6.201	2.905
41	12.65	6.194	2.769
50	13.89	6.186	2.804

TABLE VIII

Conc. of sol B'' = 24.67 g/l.
Conc. of Cl ion = 0.0047 g. ion/l.

No. of days	Sp. condy. $\times 10^3$ mho		
	Sol B''.	Sol. B''/g	Sol B''/g
0	2.63	1.479	0.742
7	2.030	1.679	0.636
23	2.565	1.763	0.663
45	2.409	1.775	0.699
61	2.789	1.796	0.8904

TABLE IX

Conc. of sol B''' = 31.63 g/l.
Conc. of Cl ion = 0.0022 g. ion/l.

No. of days	Sp. condy. $\times 10^{+4}$ mho		
	Sol B'''.	Sol B'''/g	Sol B'''/g
0	1.662	1.036	0.5408
5	2.075	1.172	0.5994
26	2.187	1.234	0.6360
49	2.160	1.233	0.6255
59	2.231	1.244	0.6299

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol and Ferric Phosphate Sol.

The sols were prepared as reported in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*) and samples were taken out at different stages of purity and designated as B, B', B'' (ferric phosphate) and C, C', C'' and C''' (V_2O_5 sol). The conductivity measurements were done at 30°.

TABLE X

Conc. of sol C—12.012 g./l.

Time.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho		
	Sol. C.	Sol C'/B.	Sol C''/B.
0 days	3.808	3.127	2.173
12	3.467	3.193	2.660
26	3.228	3.063	2.450
52	3.206	2.909	2.337
70	3.166	2.826	2.290
88	3.125	2.643	2.018

TABLE XI

Conc. of sol C'—11.466 g./l.

Time.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho		
	Sol C'.	Sol C''/B.	Sol C'''/B.
0 days	3.543	2.896	2.140
10	3.420	3.009	2.321
24	3.374	3.092	1.967
50	3.043	2.507	1.868
68	3.003	2.445	1.854
86	2.963	2.368	1.825

TABLE XII

Conc. of sol C''—10.556 g./l.

Time.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho		
	Sol C''.	Sol C'''/B.	Sol C''''/B.
0 days	3.390	2.469	1.606
8	3.345	2.950	2.093
32	3.156	2.615	2.063
47	3.013	2.757	1.966
65	2.867	2.671	1.839
83	2.717	2.601	1.683

TABLE XIII

Conc. of sol C'''—9.828 g./l.

Time.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho		
	Sol C'''.	Sol C''''/B.	Sol C'''''/B.
0 days	3.210	2.144	1.364
5	3.144	2.787	1.966
22	3.012	2.763	1.743
47	2.887	2.757	1.656
65	2.719	2.363	1.643
83	2.638	2.124	1.641

DISCUSSION

The results on the changes in electrical conductivity show that the nature of the change is different not only for the different sols, but in the case of stannic hydroxide sol it differs with the concentration of the sol investigated. An increase in conductivity in the case of diluted sols of stannic hydroxide and ferric phosphate has been noted, while there is a decrease in the concentrated sols of stannic hydroxide and vanadium pentoxide. A sol of vanadium pentoxide contains sufficient vanadic acid in solution which polymerises on ageing, and that the vanadate ions are preferentially adsorbed on the colloidal particles. This means that a sol of vanadium pentoxide would contain smaller amounts of substances in the dissolved condition when it is allowed to age, with

the consequent decrease in the electrical conductivity. In the case of dilute sols of vanadium pentoxide an increase in electrical conductivity followed by a decrease has been noted, and it appears that when a sol of vanadium pentoxide is diluted, due to the increase of the water content of the sol, more of vanadic acid ions slowly come into solution. These finally aggregate again to form polymerised molecules or colloidal particles, producing the changes in electrical conductivity as noted.

A sol of stannic hydroxide, peptised by ammonia, is a complex aggregate of ammonium stannate and we are of opinion that a sol of stannic hydroxide resembles a sol of vanadium pentoxide in this respect. Ammonium stannate in solution, on ageing undergoes hydrolysis in solution, forming colloidal stannic hydroxide. Such a chemical change in solution would necessarily result in a decrease in electrical conductivity of a stannic hydroxide sol. The decrease in conductivity of the concentrated sol of stannic hydroxide, has been noted up to a certain minimum, after which there is an increase. As it is natural tendency of all colloidal particles to give out adsorbed electrolytes with age, this explains the increase noted in the later part of the observations. In the case of dilute sols the hydrolysis is very nearly complete, and the equilibrium between adsorbed and free electrolytic ions is gradually shifted due to an excess of water being present. That is why, there is a continuous increase in the electrical conductivity of the dilute sols of stannic hydroxide, the phenomenon being most prominent with very dilute sols. In the case of ferric phosphate sols, there is in general an increase in the electrical conductivity of the sols, the changes being more prominent for the dilute sols than for the concentrated ones. In the case of concentrated sols of ferric phosphate, there has been a tendency towards increase in the electrical conductivity, although these values are not very regular because of the growth of moulds of phosphate with age.

In general, with regard to changes in electrical conductivity of sols on ageing, it may be expected that the adsorbed electrolyte on the colloidal particles shall come out, due to a decrease in the adsorbing capacity of the colloidal particles with time, resulting in an increase in the electrical conductivity of the sols on ageing. This is confirmed by our results that the dilute sols show more marked changes in conductivity. In the case of such sols, as vanadium pentoxide however, there is a decrease in the electrical conductivity, because the dissolved vanadic acid polymerises with age.